

Rigidity and Structural Asymmetry of Bounded Solutions

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Abstract

We introduce a family of parametrized non-homogeneous linear complex differential equations on $[1, \infty)$, depending on a complex parameter. We identify a *Rotation number hypothesis* on the non-homogeneous term, which a structural asymmetry between the solutions corresponding to the parameters s and $1 - \bar{s}$. More precisely, under a specific rigidity inequality, if both solutions with initial value 1 are bounded on $[1, +\infty)$, then necessarily $\Re(s) = \frac{1}{2}$.

Keywords: Non-homogeneous complex linear differential equation, bounded solutions, Euler differential equation, Volterra integral equation.

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1 Introduction and Main Result

In this manuscript, we study the following non-homogeneous linear complex differential equations:

$$\dot{\phi} = wt^{-1}\phi + t^{-1}\eta(t), \quad \phi(1) = \frac{1}{1-w}, \quad \phi : [1, +\infty) \rightarrow \mathbb{C}, \quad (1)$$

where $w \in \mathbb{C}$ such that $\Im(w) \neq 0$ is the parameter and the non-homogeneous term $\eta : [1, +\infty) \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ belongs to $L^\infty([1, \infty), \mathbb{C})$. We are interested in the initial conditions of the bounded solutions of the previous differential equation. To this end, we analyze the behavior of the transformed solution $t \mapsto (1-w)t^{-i\Im(w)}\phi(t)$, which leads us to consider the following differential equation:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{x} &= \Re(w)t^{-1}x + (1-w)t^{-1-i\Im(w)}\eta(t), \\ t &\in [1, +\infty), \quad x(1) = 1, \quad x : [1, +\infty) \rightarrow \mathbb{C}. \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Since $\eta \in L^\infty([1, \infty), \mathbb{C})$, the function

$$t \mapsto t^{\Re(w)} \int_1^t u^{-1-w} \eta(u) du, \quad t \geq 1.$$

is absolutely continuous on $[1, +\infty)$. The differential equation (2) is a non-homogeneous linear differential equation. Then, there exists a unique continuous solution $\psi_{\eta,w} : [1, +\infty) \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ of (2) such that $\psi_{\eta,w}(1) = 1$, which is given by

$$\psi_{\eta,w}(t) = t^{\Re(w)} \left[1 + (1-w) \int_1^t u^{-1-w} \eta(u) du \right], \quad \forall t \geq 1. \quad (3)$$

Let us introduce some notation.

Notation 1. For every $\eta \in L^\infty([1, \infty), \mathbb{C})$ and $w \in \mathbb{C}$, we denote by $\psi_{\eta,w}$ the unique continuous solution of the differential equation (2) given by equation (3).

Notation 2. Denote by \mathbb{C}_+ the right half-plane defined as

$$\mathbb{C}_+ := \left\{ w \in \mathbb{C} : \Re(w) > 0 \right\}.$$

For every $f \in L^\infty([1, \infty), \mathbb{C})$, let μ_f denote the function $\mu_f : \mathbb{C}_+ \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$, defined as

$$\mu_f(w) = -1 - (1-w) \int_1^{+\infty} u^{-1-w} f(u) du, \quad \forall w \in \mathbb{C}_+.$$

The function μ_f is defined for all $s \in \mathbb{C}_+$. Indeed, the integral is absolutely convergent, since $f \in L^\infty([1, \infty), \mathbb{C})$ which is bounded and since for all $w \in \mathbb{C}_+$ we have $\Re(w) > 0$.

As formulated in the Dynamical Conjecture in [3], we assume that the function η satisfies the following *Rotation number hypothesis*:

$$\exists \rho_\eta \in \mathbb{C}^* : \sup_{t \geq 1} \left| \int_1^t (\eta(u) - \rho_\eta) du \right| < +\infty, \quad (\mathbf{H})$$

The complex number ρ_η is called the *rotation number of η* .

Let us introduce the following notation.

Notation 3. Let $\eta \in L^\infty([1, \infty), \mathbb{C})$ satisfy the Rotation Number Hypothesis **(H)**. For every $x \in \mathbb{R}^*$, we denote by convention

$$\mu_\eta(ix) := 1 + \rho_\eta \frac{1 - ix}{ix} + |1 - ix|^2 \int_1^{+\infty} u^{-2-ix} \int_1^u (\eta(v) - \rho_\eta) dv du,$$

which is a well-defined complex number thanks to the Rotation Number Hypothesis **(H)**.

Using the integration by parts formula on the integral representation of μ_η given in Notation (2) (see the proof of Lemma 8, Section 3), we obtain

$$\mu_\eta(ix) = \lim_{r \rightarrow 0^+} \mu_\eta(r + ix),$$

In other words, this gives the analytic continuation of μ_η to the line $\Re(w) = 0$.

1.1 Motivation

The fractional part function $\eta_*(t) = \{t\}$ is bounded and locally integrable. Since the function $p(t) = \int_1^t (1/2 - \{u\}) du$ is 1-periodic and vanishes at integer values, it is bounded for all $t \geq 1$. Consequently, the function $\eta_*(t) = \{t\}$ satisfies hypothesis **(H)** with $\rho = \frac{1}{2}$. From the integral representation of the Riemann zeta function (Titchmarsh, [2], page 14, Equation 2.1.5):

$$\forall w \in \mathbb{C}_+ \setminus \{1\} : \frac{1-w}{w} \zeta(w) = \mu_{\eta_*}(w). \quad (4)$$

In the case of the Riemann zeta function, we obtain the analytic continuation $\mu_{\eta_*}(ix)$ given in Notation 3 from the Euler–Maclaurin formula. The following Theorem 4 makes sense when applied to the Riemann zeta function, based on the work of Hadamard [1] which guarantees that the zeta function does not vanish on the line $\Re(z) = 1$, and on the functional equation of Riemann.

1.2 Main result

We denote by $B \subset \mathbb{C}$ the the critical strip excluding the critical line and the real axis, defined by

$$B := \left\{ w \in \mathbb{C} : \Re(w) \in (0, 1), \Re(w) \neq \frac{1}{2}, \Im(w) \neq 0 \right\}. \quad (5)$$

For every $s = \sigma + i\tau \in B$, define

$$L_\eta(s, \theta) := \frac{\sigma(1-\sigma) \Re \left(\frac{\omega_s}{\alpha_\tau} \frac{\omega_s}{i\tau} \left(\beta_\tau + \frac{\exp(i\theta)}{1+i\tau} \right) \right)}{\Re \left(\overline{\alpha_\tau} \left(\beta_\tau - (\omega_\tau - \omega_s) \rho_\eta \exp(i\theta) \right) \right)}, \quad \forall \theta \in [0, 2\pi],$$

with

$$\alpha_\tau := -\mu_\eta(1 + i\tau), \quad \beta_\tau := -\mu_\eta(i\tau), \quad \omega_\tau := \frac{1}{i\tau(1 + i\tau)} \quad \text{and} \quad \omega_s := \frac{1}{s(1 - \bar{s})},$$

where $\mu_\eta(1 + i\tau)$ and $\mu_\eta(i\tau)$ are as given in Notations 2 and 3.

We will see in Lemma 8 of Section 3 that, for every $w \in \mathbb{C}_+$, the solution $\psi_{\eta,w}$ is bounded on $[1, +\infty)$ if and only if $\mu_\eta(w) = 0$. The following main result provides an answer to the Dynamical Conjecture formulated in [3]. More precisely, we show that if the function η satisfies the rotation number hypothesis **(H)** then under a specific *Rigidity inequality*, the symmetric continuous solutions $\psi_{\eta,w}$ and $\psi_{\eta,1-\bar{w}}$ of the differential equation (2) cannot both be bounded on $[1, +\infty)$.

Theorem 4. *Let $\eta \in L^\infty([1, \infty), \mathbb{C})$ satisfy the Rotation Number Hypothesis **(H)**, and let $s = \sigma + i\tau \in B$. Assume that $\mu_\eta(1 + i\tau) \neq 0$ and $L_\eta(s, \theta) \neq 0$ for all $\theta \in [0, 2\pi]$. Then $(\mu_\eta(s), \mu_\eta(1 - \bar{s})) \neq (0, 0)$.*

2 Main Proposition

In this section, the results hold for any $\eta \in L^\infty([1, \infty), \mathbb{C})$. In other words, we do not consider the Rotation Number Hypothesis **(H)**.

Let us introduce the following notation.

Notation 5. Let $\eta \in L^\infty([1, \infty), \mathbb{C})$. Consider the continuous solutions of the differential equation (2) as given in Notation 1. For every $w \in \mathbb{C}$ with $\Re(w) \neq \frac{1}{2}$, we denote by $\delta_{\eta,w} : [1, +\infty) \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ the function

$$\delta_{\eta,w}(t) := \frac{1}{2\Re(w) - 1} \left(\psi_{\eta,w}(t) - \psi_{\eta,1-\bar{w}}(t) \right), \quad \forall t \geq 1.$$

The differential equation (2) can be viewed as a differential equation with the parameter $\Re(w)$. Intuitively, this introduces an order structure within the set of solutions with the same initial condition and parameterized by $\Re(w)$. We start to exhibit this order between solutions through the following proposition.

Proposition 6. *Let $\eta \in L^\infty([1, \infty), \mathbb{C})$. For every $s = \sigma + i\tau \in \mathbb{C}$ with $\sigma \neq \frac{1}{2}$, the functions $\delta_{\eta,s}$ and $\delta_{\eta,1+i\tau}$, defined in Notation 5, satisfy the following Euler differential equation:*

$$\frac{d^2}{dt^2} \left(\delta_{\eta,1+i\tau}(t) - \delta_{\eta,s}(t) \right) = \sigma(1 - \sigma)t^{-2} \delta_{\eta,s}(t), \quad \forall t \geq 1,$$

with initial conditions $\delta_{\eta,s}(1) = \delta_{\eta,1+i\tau}(1) = 0$ and $\dot{\delta}_{\eta,1+i\tau}(1) - \dot{\delta}_{\eta,s}(1) = 0$.

Remark 7. The proof of the previous proposition can be carried out by simply differentiating twice with respect to t the function $\delta_{\eta,1+i\tau} - \delta_{\eta,s}$. After the first differentiation, each expression of $\dot{\delta}_{\eta,1+i\tau}$ and $\dot{\delta}_{\eta,s}$ contains a non-differentiable term involving η . However, these non-differentiable terms cancel out through an algebraic combination, which makes it possible to differentiate a second time. The method of the following proof establishes that $\delta_{\eta,1+i\tau} - \delta_{\eta,s}$ is twice differentiable.

Proof of the Proposition 6. Let $w \in \mathbb{C}$ and denote $w := \alpha + i\beta$. For every $t \geq 1$ denote

$$x_w(t) := t^{-\frac{1}{2}}\psi_{\eta,w}(t). \quad (6)$$

According to Notation 1, we obtain the following differential equation

$$\dot{x}_w(t) = \left(\alpha - \frac{1}{2}\right)t^{-1}x_w(t) + (1-w)t^{-\frac{3}{2}-i\beta}\eta(t), \quad x_w(1) = 1. \quad (7)$$

Let $s := \sigma + i\tau \in \mathbb{C}$ with $\sigma \neq \frac{1}{2}$. From the previous equation, we have

$$\dot{x}_s(t) + \dot{x}_{1-\bar{s}}(t) = \left(\sigma - \frac{1}{2}\right)t^{-1}(x_s(t) - x_{1-\bar{s}}(t)) + (1-2i\tau)t^{-\frac{3}{2}-i\tau}\eta(t).$$

Use the fact that $x_s(1) = x_{1-\bar{s}}(1) = 1$ and integrate, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} x_s(t) + x_{1-\bar{s}}(t) &= \left(\sigma - \frac{1}{2}\right) \int_1^t u^{-1}(x_s(u) - x_{1-\bar{s}}(u)) du \\ &\quad + 2 + (1-2i\tau) \int_1^t u^{-\frac{3}{2}-i\tau}\eta(u) du. \end{aligned}$$

From the differential equation (7), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{x}_s(t) - \dot{x}_{1-\bar{s}}(t) &= \left(\sigma - \frac{1}{2}\right)t^{-1}(x_s(t) + x_{1-\bar{s}}(t)) \\ &\quad - (2\sigma - 1)t^{-\frac{3}{2}-i\tau}\eta(t). \end{aligned}$$

The two previous differential equations give

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{x}_s(t) - \dot{x}_{1-\bar{s}}(t) &= \left(\sigma - \frac{1}{2}\right)^2 t^{-1} \int_1^t u^{-1}(x_s(u) - x_{1-\bar{s}}(u)) du \\ &\quad + (2\sigma - 1)t^{-1} \left[1 + \left(\frac{1}{2} - i\tau\right) \int_1^t u^{-\frac{3}{2}-i\tau}\eta(u) du \right] \\ &\quad - (2\sigma - 1)t^{-\frac{3}{2}-i\tau}\eta(t). \end{aligned}$$

Use the fact that $x_s(1) - x_{1-\bar{s}}(1) = 0$ and integrate, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} x_s(t) - x_{1-\bar{s}}(t) &= (\sigma - \frac{1}{2})^2 \int_1^t u^{-1} \int_1^u v^{-1} (x_s(v) - x_{1-\bar{s}}(v)) dv du \\ &\quad + (2\sigma - 1) \int_1^t u^{-1} \left[1 + (\frac{1}{2} - i\tau) \int_1^u v^{-\frac{3}{2}-i\tau} \eta(v) dv \right] du \\ &\quad - (2\sigma - 1) \int_1^t u^{-\frac{3}{2}-i\tau} \eta(u) du. \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

By definition of x_w in equation (6), we have

$$x_s(t) - x_{1-\bar{s}}(t) = t^{-\frac{1}{2}} (\psi_{\eta,s}(t) - \psi_{\eta,1-\bar{s}}(t)).$$

By the Notation 5, we have

$$\delta_{\eta,s}(t) = \frac{1}{2\sigma - 1} (\psi_{\eta,s}(t) - \psi_{\eta,1-\bar{s}}(t)).$$

Then

$$x_s(t) - x_{1-\bar{s}}(t) = (2\sigma - 1)t^{-\frac{1}{2}} \delta_{\eta,s}(t),$$

In terms of $\delta_{\eta,s}$ the integral equation (8) becomes

$$\begin{aligned} t^{-\frac{1}{2}} \delta_{\eta,s}(t) &= (\sigma - \frac{1}{2})^2 \int_1^t u^{-1} \int_1^u v^{-\frac{3}{2}} \delta_{\eta,s}(v) dv du \\ &\quad + \int_1^t u^{-1} \left[1 + (\frac{1}{2} - i\tau) \int_1^u v^{-\frac{3}{2}-i\tau} \eta(v) dv \right] du \\ &\quad - \int_1^t u^{-\frac{3}{2}-i\tau} \eta(u) du. \end{aligned}$$

In particular when $\sigma := \Re(s) = 1$, we get

$$\begin{aligned} t^{-\frac{1}{2}} \delta_{\eta,1+i\tau}(t) &= \frac{1}{4} \int_1^t u^{-1} \int_1^u v^{-\frac{3}{2}} \delta_{\eta,1+i\tau}(v) dv du \\ &\quad + \int_1^t u^{-1} \left[1 + (\frac{1}{2} - i\tau) \int_1^u v^{-\frac{3}{2}-i\tau} \eta(v) dv \right] du \\ &\quad - \int_1^t u^{-\frac{3}{2}-i\tau} \eta(u) du. \end{aligned}$$

Subtracting the two previous equations gives the following Volterra integral equation:

$$\begin{aligned} \delta_{\eta,1+i\tau}(t) - \delta_{\eta,s}(t) &= \frac{1}{4} t^{\frac{1}{2}} \int_1^t u^{-1} \int_1^u v^{-\frac{3}{2}} \delta_{\eta,1+i\tau}(v) dv du \\ &\quad - (\sigma - \frac{1}{2})^2 t^{\frac{1}{2}} \int_1^t u^{-1} \int_1^u v^{-\frac{3}{2}} \delta_{\eta,s}(v) dv du, \quad \forall t \geq 1. \end{aligned}$$

After differentiating twice, we obtain the following Euler differential equation:

$$\frac{d^2}{dt^2} \left(\delta_{\eta,1+i\tau}(t) - \delta_{\eta,s}(t) \right) = \sigma(1-\sigma)t^{-2}\delta_{\eta,s}(t), \quad \forall t \geq 1,$$

with initial conditions $\delta_{\eta,s}(1) = \delta_{\eta,1+i\tau}(1) = 0$ and $\dot{\delta}_{\eta,s}(1) - \dot{\delta}_{\eta,1+i\tau}(1) = 0$. \square

3 Main Lemmas

In the following two lemmas, we consider the continuous solution $\psi_{\eta,w}$ of the differential equation (2), as introduced in Notation 1, and study its asymptotic behavior.

Lemma 8. *Let $\eta \in L^\infty([1, \infty), \mathbb{C})$ satisfy the Rotation Number Hypothesis **(H)**, with rotation number ρ_η . Then, for all $w \in \mathbb{C}_+$ the function $\epsilon_w : [1, +\infty) \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ defined as*

$$\epsilon_w(t) := \psi_{\eta,w}(t) + \mu_\eta(w)t^{\Re(w)} + \rho_\eta \frac{1-w}{w} t^{-i\Im(w)}, \quad \forall t \geq 1,$$

satisfies the following equation

$$\sup_{t \geq 1} |t \epsilon_w(t)| < +\infty.$$

Furthermore, for every $x \in \mathbb{R}^*$ the function $\epsilon_x : [1, +\infty) \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ defined as

$$\epsilon_x(t) := \psi_{\eta,ix}(t) + \mu_\eta(ix) + \rho_\eta \frac{1-ix}{ix} t^{-ix}, \quad \forall t \geq 1,$$

satisfies the following equation

$$\sup_{t \geq 1} |t \epsilon_x(t)| < +\infty,$$

where $\mu_\eta(ix)$ is given by the notation 3. In addition, we have

$$\int_1^t u^{-1} \psi_{\eta,w}(u) du = \frac{1}{\Re(w)} \left(\psi_{\eta,w}(t) - 1 \right) - \frac{1-w}{\Re(w)(1-i\Im(w))} \left(\psi_{\eta,i\Im(w)}(t) - 1 \right).$$

Proof. By definition of $\mu_\eta(w)$ in Notation 2, we have

$$\mu_\eta(w) + 1 + (1-w) \int_1^t u^{-1-w} \eta(u) du = -(1-w) \int_t^{+\infty} u^{-1-w} \eta(u) du, \quad \forall t \geq 1.$$

From equation (3), we obtain

$$\psi_{\eta,w}(t) = -\mu_{\eta}(w)t^{\Re(w)} - (1-w)t^{\Re(w)} \int_t^{+\infty} u^{-1-w}\eta(u) du, \quad \forall t \geq 1. \quad (9)$$

By hypothesis the function η satisfies the hypothesis **(H)** with rotation number ρ_{η} . Then there exists $c > 0$ such that

$$\left| \int_1^t (\eta(u) - \rho_{\eta}) du \right| < c, \quad \forall t \geq 1.$$

Implies

$$\left| \int_t^u (\eta(u) - \rho_{\eta}) du \right| < 2c, \quad \forall u \geq t \geq 1. \quad (10)$$

Hence, the equation (9) can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \psi_{\eta,w}(t) &= -\mu_{\eta}(w)t^{\Re(w)} - \rho_{\eta} \frac{1-w}{w} t^{-i\Im(w)} \\ &\quad - (1-w)t^{\Re(w)} \int_t^{+\infty} u^{-1-w}(\eta(u) - \rho_{\eta}) du, \end{aligned}$$

In other words

$$\psi_{\eta,w}(t) + \mu_{\eta}(w)t^{\Re(w)} + \rho_{\eta} \frac{1-w}{w} t^{-i\Im(w)} = \epsilon_w(t), \quad \forall t \geq 1,$$

where

$$\epsilon_w(t) = -(1-w)t^{\Re(w)} \int_t^{+\infty} u^{-1-w}(\eta(u) - \rho_{\eta}) du,$$

Using equation equation (10) and the integration by parts formula, we obtain

$$\epsilon_w(t) := -(1-w^2)t^{\Re(w)} \int_t^{+\infty} u^{-2-w} \int_t^u (\eta(v) - \rho_{\eta}) dv du, \quad \forall t \geq 1,$$

which is a C^1 function and, thanks to equation (10), satisfies the following inequality for every $t \geq 1$:

$$\sup_{t \geq 1} |t\epsilon_w(t)| < +\infty.$$

Now, prove the second item of the lemma. The function $\psi_{\eta,ix}$ is the continuous solutions of the differential equation (2), as introduced in Notation 1 and given by equation (3) as:

$$\psi_{\eta,ix}(t) = 1 + (1-ix) \int_1^t u^{-1-ix}\eta(u) du, \quad \forall t \geq 1. \quad (11)$$

which can be written as

$$\psi_{\eta,ix}(t) = 1 + \rho_{\eta} \frac{1-ix}{ix} (1-t^{-ix}) + (1-ix) \int_1^t u^{-1-ix} (\eta(u) - \rho_{\eta}) du.$$

Use the integration by formula and use the equation (10), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \psi_{\eta,ix}(t) &= 1 + \rho_{\eta} \frac{1-ix}{ix} (1-t^{-ix}) + (1-ix)t^{-1-ix} \int_1^t (\eta(v) - \rho_{\eta}) dv \\ &\quad + |1-ix|^2 \int_1^t u^{-2-ix} \int_1^u (\eta(v) - \rho_{\eta}) dv du. \end{aligned}$$

Thanks to the notation 3, we have

$$\begin{aligned} 1 + \rho_{\eta} \frac{1-ix}{ix} + |1-ix|^2 \int_1^t u^{-2-ix} \int_1^u (\eta(v) - \rho_{\eta}) dv du \\ = -\mu_{\eta}(ix) - |1-ix|^2 \int_t^{+\infty} u^{-2-ix} \int_t^u (\eta(v) - \rho_{\eta}) dv du. \end{aligned}$$

Using equation (10), for all $t \geq 1$ we get

$$\left| \psi_{\eta,ix}(t) + \mu_{\eta}(ix) + \rho_{\eta} \frac{1-ix}{ix} t^{-ix} \right| < c_x t^{-1}.$$

The function $\psi_{\eta,w}$ is the continuous solutions of the differential equation (2),

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\psi}_{\eta,w}(t) &= \Re(w)t^{-1}\psi_{\eta,w}(t) + (1-w)t^{-1-i\Im(w)}\eta(t), \\ t \in [1, +\infty), \quad x(1) &= 1, \quad x : [1, +\infty) \rightarrow \mathbb{C}. \end{aligned}$$

Integrate

$$\frac{1}{\Re(w)} \psi_{\eta,w}(t) = \int_1^t u^{-1}\psi_{\eta,w}(u) du + \frac{1}{\Re(w)} + \frac{1-w}{\Re(w)} \int_1^t u^{-1-i\Im(w)}\eta(u) du,$$

Denote $x := \Im(w)$, by equation (11) we have

$$\int_1^t u^{-1-ix}\eta(u) du = \frac{1}{1-ix} (\psi_{\eta,ix}(t) - 1), \quad \forall t \geq 1.$$

It follows that

$$\int_1^t u^{-1}\psi_{\eta,w}(u) du = \frac{1}{\Re(w)} \psi_{\eta,w}(t) - \frac{1}{\Re(w)} - \frac{1-w}{\Re(w)(1-ix)} (\psi_{\eta,ix}(t) - 1).$$

□

4 Proof of the Theorem 4

Proof of the Theorem 4. Let $\eta \in L^\infty([1, \infty), \mathbb{C})$ satisfy the Rotation Number Hypothesis **(H)**. . We prove the theorem by contradiction. Let $s := \sigma + i\tau \in B$ such that $\mu_\eta(1 + i\tau) \neq 0$ and suppose that $(\mu_\eta(s), \mu_\eta(1 - \bar{s})) = (0, 0)$. From the first item of the Lemma 8, for $w \in \{s, 1 - \bar{s}, 1 + i\tau\}$ the function $\epsilon_w : [1, +\infty) \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ defined as

$$\epsilon_w(t) := \psi_{\eta,w}(t) + \mu_\eta(w)t^{\Re(w)} + \rho_\eta \frac{1-w}{w} t^{-i\tau}, \quad \forall t \geq 1,$$

satisfies the following equation

$$\sup_{t \geq 1} |t \epsilon_w(t)| < +\infty. \quad (12)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \int_1^t u^{-1} \psi_{\eta,w}(u) du &= \frac{1}{\Re(w)} (\psi_{\eta,w}(t) - 1) \\ &\quad - \frac{1-w}{\Re(w)(1-i\Im(w))} (\psi_{\eta,i\Im(w)}(t) - 1). \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

We recall that the function $\delta_{\eta,w}$ is defined in Notation 5 as

$$\delta_{\eta,w}(t) := \frac{1}{2\Re(w) - 1} (\psi_{\eta,w}(t) - \psi_{\eta,1-\bar{w}}(t)), \quad \forall w \in \mathbb{C}, \Re(w) \neq \frac{1}{2}, \forall t \geq 1.$$

Since $(\mu_\eta(s), \mu_\eta(1 - \bar{s})) = (0, 0)$, using the fact that

$$\frac{1}{2\sigma - 1} \left(\frac{1-s}{s} - \frac{\bar{s}}{1-\bar{s}} \right) = -\frac{1}{s(1-\bar{s})},$$

the equation (12), implies that

$$\sup_{t \geq 1} \left| t \delta_{\eta,s}(t) - \frac{\rho_\eta}{s(1-\bar{s})} t^{1-i\tau} \right| < +\infty, \quad (14)$$

Denote

$$\alpha_\tau := -\mu_\eta(1 + i\tau) \quad \text{and} \quad \beta_\tau := -\mu_\eta(i\tau),$$

From the second item of the Lemma 8, we have

$$\sup_{t \geq 1} \left| \psi_{\eta,i\tau}(t) - \beta_\tau + \rho_\eta \frac{1-i\tau}{i\tau} t^{-i\tau} \right| < +\infty,$$

Thanks to equation (13) and (12), we have

$$\sup_{t \geq 1} \left| t \left((2\sigma - 1) \int_1^t u^{-1} \delta_{\eta,s}(u) du - f_s(t) \right) \right| < +\infty, \quad (15)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} f_s(t) := & -\frac{1}{\sigma} \left(1 + \rho_\eta \frac{1-s}{s} t^{-i\tau} \right) + \frac{1}{1-\sigma} \left(1 + \rho_\eta \frac{\bar{s}}{1-\bar{s}} t^{-i\tau} \right) \\ & - \frac{1}{1-i\tau} \left(\frac{1-s}{\sigma} - \frac{1-\bar{s}}{1-\sigma} \right) \left(\beta_\tau - \rho_\eta \frac{1-i\tau}{i\tau} t^{-i\tau} - 1 \right) \end{aligned}$$

and we have

$$\sup_{t \geq 1} \left| t \delta_{\eta,1+i\tau}(t) + \mu_\eta(1+i\tau)t^2 - \mu_\eta(i\tau)t - \frac{\rho_\eta}{i\tau(1+i\tau)} t^{1-i\tau} \right| < +\infty,$$

or

$$\sup_{t \geq 1} \left| t \delta_{\eta,1+i\tau}(t) - \alpha_\tau t^2 + \beta_\tau t - \frac{\rho_\eta}{i\tau(1+i\tau)} t^{1-i\tau} \right| < +\infty, \quad (16)$$

where $\mu_\eta(i\tau)$ is as given by the notation 3. In order to simplify the notation, define

$$\widehat{\delta}_s(t) := \delta_{\eta,1+i\tau}(t) - \delta_{\eta,s}(t), \quad \forall t \geq 1. \quad (17)$$

Equations (14) and (16), implies

$$\sup_{t \geq 1} \left| t \widehat{\delta}_s(t) - \alpha_\tau t^2 + \beta_\tau t - \rho_\eta(\omega_\tau - \omega_s) t^{1-i\tau} \right| < +\infty, \quad (18)$$

where

$$\omega_\tau := \frac{1}{i\tau(1+i\tau)} \quad \omega_s := \frac{1}{s(1-\bar{s})}.$$

By Proposition 6, we have the following Euler differential equation:

$$\ddot{\widehat{\delta}}_s(t) = \sigma(1-\sigma)t^{-2}\delta_{\eta,s}(t), \quad \forall t \geq 1, \quad (19)$$

with initial conditions $\delta_{\eta,s}(1) = \delta_{\eta,1+i\tau}(1) = 0$ and $\dot{\delta}_{\eta,1+i\tau}(1) - \dot{\delta}_{\eta,s}(1) = 0$. Multiplying the previous equation by t and integrating, then applying integration by parts formula, we obtain

$$t \dot{\widehat{\delta}}_s(t) - \widehat{\delta}_s(t) = \sigma(1-\sigma) \int_1^t u^{-1} \delta_{\eta,s}(u) du, \quad \forall t \geq 1,$$

equivalently,

$$\frac{d}{dt} \left(t^{-1} \widehat{\delta}_s(t) \right) = \sigma(1-\sigma)t^{-2} \int_1^t u^{-1} \delta_{\eta,s}(u) du, \quad \forall t \geq 1.$$

Multiplying by the complex conjugate of $t^{-1}\widehat{\delta}_s(t)$ and taking the real part, one obtains

$$\frac{d}{dt} \left| t^{-1}\widehat{\delta}_s(t) \right|^2 = 2\sigma(1-\sigma)t^{-3} \Re \left(\overline{\widehat{\delta}_s(t)} \int_1^t u^{-1}\delta_{\eta,s}(u) du \right), \quad \forall t \geq 1.$$

Integrate, for all $t_2 > t_1 > 1$, we get

$$\left| t_2^{-1}\widehat{\delta}_s(t_2) \right|^2 - \left| t_1^{-1}\widehat{\delta}_s(t_1) \right|^2 = 2\sigma(1-\sigma) \int_{t_1}^{t_2} v^{-3} \Re \left(\overline{\widehat{\delta}_s(v)} \int_1^v u^{-1}\delta_{\eta,s}(u) du \right) dv.$$

It follows that,

$$1 = \frac{2\sigma(1-\sigma) \int_{t_1}^{t_2} v^{-3} \Re \left(\overline{\widehat{\delta}_s(v)} \int_1^v u^{-1}\delta_{\eta,s}(u) du \right) dv}{\left| t_2^{-1}\widehat{\delta}_s(t_2) \right|^2 - \left| t_1^{-1}\widehat{\delta}_s(t_1) \right|^2}.$$

Thanks to the estimations give by equations (14) and (18), asymptotically there exists a real sequence $(t_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ with $\lim_{n \rightarrow +\infty} t_n = +\infty$ such that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow +\infty} \frac{\sigma(1-\sigma) \Re \left[\overline{\alpha_\tau} \frac{\omega_s}{i\tau} \left(\beta_\tau + \frac{t_n^{-i\tau}}{1+i\tau} \right) \right]}{\Re(\overline{\alpha_\tau}\beta_\tau) - \Re(\overline{\alpha_\tau}(\omega_\tau - \omega_s)\rho_\eta t_n^{-i\tau})} = 0,$$

with

$$\beta_\tau := -\mu_\eta(i\tau), \quad \omega_\tau := \frac{1}{i\tau(1+i\tau)} \quad \text{and} \quad \omega_s := \frac{1}{s(1-\bar{s})}.$$

□

References

- [1] J. Hadamard, Sur la distribution des zéros de la fonction $\zeta(s)$ et ses conséquences arithmétiques, Bull. Soc. Math. France, 24, 199–220. (1896)
- [2] E.C. Titchmarsh, The Theory of the Riemann Zeta-Function (revised by D.R. Heath-Brown), Clarendon Press, Oxford. (1986)
- [3] W. Oukil, Bounded Solutions of a Complex Differential Equation for the Riemann Hypothesis. HAL Id : hal-03849860. <https://hal.science/hal-03849860>. (2025).